

SCIENTIFIC FOUNDATIONS OF THE ORGANIZATION PROCESS OF STUDENTS' INCREASING SPEAKING SKILL INDEPENDENTLY AND IMPORTANCE OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Khusanova Sevinch¹, Bakhora Boboeva², Bannopova Zulhumor³

¹First-year student of the Philology faculty of the Uzbekistan state world languages university, sevinckhusanova@gmail.com
+998912270617

²Second-year student of the Philology faculty of the Uzbekistan state world languages university, bakhora.boboyeva@gmail.com
+998944792141

³Scientific adviser: Teacher of the philology faculty of Uzbekistan state world language university,
+998977471855

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6657721>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th May 2022
Accepted: 02nd June 2022
Online: 05th June 2022

KEY WORDS

*independent work,
speaking skill, foreign
language, advanced
vocabulary, self-study, ted
talk, factors enhancing.*

ABSTRACT

This article aims to identify alternative methods and techniques based on scientific approaches for students who want to learn a foreign language independently. Moreover, it solves the main issue encountered in the organization of the language learning process which is as enhancing speaking skills among learners. Importantly, written about scientifically based views on the importance of learning foreign languages for students.

Introduction

Nowadays, learning foreign languages (LFL) is turning into a crucial activity among other, speaking foreign languages is a significant skill in today's globalized world. Especially, English. Students learn foreign languages for many reasons, such as visited to abroad or get a job, probably, they want to carry on their study in the foreign countries of the Europe after university, whatever the reason, the beneficial sides can be incredibly worthwhile. Learning a foreign language (LFL) not only can give you chance to achieve a successful career for your future but also, make an opportunity to gain cultural knowledge and can help you built more confidence when you go foreign

country. It's also a fact that learning a second language raise brain activity functionality. Moreover, if you know some foreign language, you can study all over the world. Since English is used in a lot of different countries there are so many companies and universities around the world that offer programs in English. If you have a sufficient level of academic English, there are more and more opportunities for you to find an appropriate profession and work place according to your desire. However, studying a foreign language is not an easy task for some learners. The majority part of students faces same problem during learning foreign language. Today, students have not enough experience and knowledge in independent

work, therefore, they are not capable of improving their academic level of English, especially, in speaking skill.

To begin with, the most common problem came across by learners during studying foreign languages is that some students are worried to speak in front of people, because they consider that they will not be capable of speaking that language fluently or they will not be able to reply without some mistakes, that is why, may allow to be embarrassed during communicating with others. And these all situations be reason to make hesitation while speaking

DISCUSSION

As mentioned above, the importance of learning a language is growing day by day, and the ability of each learner to use an intensive approach also plays a significant role in accelerating and facilitating this process which is improving speaking skill. The challenge of learning a foreign language (LFL) is part of what makes going through the difficulties worth it. There is a feeling of empowerment once you master a language. Of course, it can be quite frustrating at times while you are in the learning process Still, each difficult helps propel you forward to fluency. This means that we need to identify the main reasons for not being able to develop speaking skills while learning a foreign language.

1 making confusing and common grammar mistakes while speaking in foreign language:

The main reason why students confuse and make grammatical mistakes when speaking English is that they attempt to translate their thoughts into English while find appropriate vocabulary on their mind while speaking, this does not give a chance them to pay attention to the grammatical structure and rules of speech. To overcome

this error, initially the student must develop the ability to think in English. So, it may become part of your “inner speech.” In other words, you start thinking in that language. Your mind stops trying to translate things from your native language into another language.

Why think in English can play a crucial role to get rid of grammar mistakes?

As you know, every language has their own grammatical rules and orders for making sentence. If you do not increase the ability to think in the language which you spoken, it makes confuse you while speaking. The best and most effective way to prevent this and to develop thinking in English is to create an atmosphere in the language you are learning and not go out of that zone. For instance,

Start by called all the objects in your room in English; change your language settings on your smartphone also and all the social media you use to the turn language (English); star to make a habit listen to music (sing along) and podcasts in that language; watching videos and films with subtitles in target language; find a native language partner who can talk to you, idly every day, read and write a lot. The methods listed above not only contribute to the development of thinking in English, but also to the increase of public speaking. When students trying to learn a foreign language independently what they actually know to focus on, then in any case their language learning skills will not stop developing. I also give an example of this: no one learns grammatical rules in their own language first and then starts speaking. Everyone first develops the ability to speak because of the environment that surrounds them. When you can create your environment properly, you can

effectively eliminate not only grammatical errors, but also any problems encountered during speaking.

2. Lack of confidence in speaking foreign language:

It is natural for the learner to have strong fears and doubts when speaking any foreign language. Lack of confidence learn English language need a get experience and have to be patient. However, the common problem of learners is that, they are not sufficient confidence when they are communicating in English, someone is not power of themselves to speak, therefore, they are unable to remember the grammar rules and correct vocabulary in speaking foreign language. Making mistakes is not a scary situation. No one is born with a brilliant talent for speaking in a foreign language. Everyone has error but they should learn from their mistakes and try to overcome their problem in during getting a foreign language.

What is the main reason for this situation?

Lake of appropriate and advanced vocabulary,

inability to use alternative grammatical structures,

underdeveloped public speaking ability

Initially, there are more and more that types of problems but as you know, all have their own solutions. For example, there are many online platforms and projects for anyone who wants to learn English independently and improve their speaking skills also. The most popular and well-known platform which is I can recommend without hesitation is BBC Learning English. It is a department of the BBC World Service devoted to English language teaching. The service provides free resources and activities for teachers and students, primarily through its website.

BBC Learning English - 6 Minute English

By engaging in this platform on a regular basis, students will not only be able to maximize their vocabulary, but will also be

able to develop the ability to use correct grammatical structures.

Another useful program is the TED TALK project. *"TED is dedicated to researching and sharing knowledge that matters through short talks and presentations. Our goal is to inform*

and educate global audiences in an accessible way”.

<https://www.ted.com/>

Through this project, any independent language learner will be able to think quickly and clearly and gain a conference he or she needs from each speaker. It also allows you to create the aforementioned English zone.

RESULT

To begin with, every student who works independently has a great opportunity to learn foreign languages easily and effectively, if he can accurately assess his abilities. Shame in the process of speaking, or fear of mistakes, makes your self-confidence completely disappear, therefore, built a conference with the same level gain an updated knowledge. If the student can study all the above problems and solutions correctly, he or she will achieve an unprecedented accomplishment. In *Independent work language learners should take full responsibility for the whole process of studying. It's deciding for yourself what you desire learning and in what way you want to learn it. It's about autonomy. It's about*

having the freedom to customize one's learning experience.

CONCLUSION

In Today's globalized world, the study of foreign languages plays an important role in every aspect. We all witness that the majority of young people are working hard to learn a language on their own. Although language is a humanitarian field, it involves in many difficult processes therefore, it is natural to encounter many problems in it. Especially speech development is more complex than developing other aspects of language. However, *English is used by approximately 360 million people around the world and, students are learning that language as a subject in 118 countries. In addition to this, English language learning will give you a chance to communicate effectively with people around the world* So, every language learner should understand the importance of knowing foreign languages and focus on developing with alternative approach to making easier the process of improving speaking ability during language learning.

References:

1. Boonkit, K. Enhancing the development of speaking skills for non-native speakers of English. / K. Boonkit. — Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences. — 2010. — Volume 2, Issue 2, DOI:10.1016/j.sbspro.2010.03.191
2. GT IELTS. Essay 39 – Living in a country where you have to speak a foreign language. — IELTS General Training. — 2021. <https://www.ielts-gt.com/writing-task-2-sample/living-in-country-where-you-have-to-speak-foreign-language>
3. Kendallhurley. Make Foreign Language Acquisition Less “Ruff” with 5 Simple Tips! / Kendallhurley. — FluentU. — 2021. <https://www.fluentu.com/blog/foreign-language-acquisition/>.
4. Navarro, B. Improving Speaking Skills. / B. Navarro. — Encuentro. — 2009. — №18
5. TED Talks. A lot goes into researching and creating a TED Talk. — 2019. <https://www.ted.com/about/programs-initiatives/ted-talks>
<https://www.ted.com/https://www.fluentu.com/>
6. Schreyer, M. 16 Effective Language Learning Strategies For Mastering a Foreign Language. / M. Schreyer. — SMD Magazine. — 2021. <https://sustainabilitymattersdaily.com/language-learning-strategies>
7. Wahyuniati. Improving Speaking Skill Through Speaking Club Viewed from Students' Perception. / Wahyuniati, N. Maulidiyah, M. Qolbia. — Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research. — 2020. — Volume: 434, DOI:10.2991/assehr.k.200427.026